

ISic1115

I.Sicily inscription 1115

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Alcamo

Provenance

Santa Maria (?)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Alcamo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140598

1. Δ (αίμοσι) Χ (θονίοις) .
2. Δόμνα ἔζ[η]σεν [ἔτη —],
3. μῆν (ας) ἠ'. Βόττος [καὶ Με]-
4. λιτίνη τέκ[ν]ω [γλυκυτάτω]
5. ἐπ[οίησαν].
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492731

EDCS 39102272

PHI 140598

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0294 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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